

Librarianship Students' Awareness Of Open Educational Resources Copyright

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Abstract

The research is aimed at finding solutions to raise awareness of librarianship students at Can Tho University of open educational resources copyright. The study was conducted using the quantitative method with 160 survey samples from the students of Library and Information Management. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS software. The research findings show that the librarianship students' knowledge of open educational resources is very low. Moreover, their awareness of open educational resources copyright and their usage of this resource are still limited. This is an alarming issue for librarianship students and the university in performing copyright to this useful learning resource.

Introduction

Open Educational Resources (OER) are freely accessible and used resources for learning and research purposes. Therefore, OER is being considered as an effective scientific information resource to support the universalization of education and become an indispensable development trend in the academic environment. Universities in the world including Can Tho University (CTU) always reserve it as a part on their website or in the library for users. However, a large number of students, including students majoring in Library and Information Science used this resource without citing. What is the cause? Is it because of their unawareness of copyright or is it due to another reason? Therefore, it is necessary to have a study to evaluate this matter among librarianship students to protect and attract more authors contribute to this source. In particular, research needs to be done with librarianship students because they are the potential librarians and information specialists. If there is no timely assessment and remedial solution, incorrect conceptions and perceptions about copyright will still affect future generations of users. Moreover, the fact that students search and share documents to serve their learning and research needs without citing is a state alarming affair. Copyright infringement will greatly affect the economy as well as the culture, reduce the enthusiasm and creativity of researchers, create anxiety for researchers when the works are published and used for commercial purposes, without attribution or appropriation of their own works.

The study aims to contribute to raising the students' awareness, including librarianship students about the meaning and importance of respecting the World Trade Organization for OER. The research findings are expected to be of great help not only to the librarianship students, but also to the Department of Library and Information Management, School of Social Sciences and Humanities and Can Tho University. This research helps students realize the role of OER and their own copyright violations towards this resource. Importantly, students will obey as well as propagate to friends and relatives more aware of the copyright protection. In addition, this study helps the academics better understand students' perceptions of international law violations during their study at the university, thereby offering solutions that contribute to raising their awareness and practice for OER. The teachers will promptly remind and educate students. Moreover, the research helps the university to have more evidence to make appropriate regulations and policies related to OER for the students in contributing to improving the quality of training, increasing the university prestige and trust from the community and society.

Methodology and literature review Copyright

Copyright is the author's exclusive rights to his or her own work. In Vietnam, the Law on Intellectual Property 2005 (amended in 2009) stipulates that copyright means rights of an organization or individual to works which such organization or individual created or owns. Copyright shall arise at the moment a work is created and fixed in a certain material form, irrespective of its content, quality, form, mode and language and irrespective of whether or not such work has been published or registered. Copyright comprises moral rights and economic rights. Moral rights comprise the rights to give titles to their works; to attach their real names or pseudonyms to their works, to have their real names or pseudonyms acknowledged when their works are published or used; to publish their works or to authorize other persons to publish their works; and to protect the integrity of their works, forbid other persons to modify, edit or distort their works in whatever form, causing harm to the honor and reputation of the author. Economic rights comprise the rights to make derivative works; to display their works to the public; to reproduce their works; to distribute or import the original or copies of their works; to communicate their works to the public by wireless or landline means, electronic information networks or other technical means; and to lease the original or copies of cinematographic works and computer programs.

Copyright protection

Copyright protection is extremely important because this is the result of the investment of time and effort of individuals/ collectives. For the creator, the copyright protection creates a relation between the author and the work, while creating motivation for the author to create a new work. The State requires all individuals to protect the copyright through the regulation of the integrity of the work even if it is disseminated to the public. It is important for the author to receive compensation from the work he created. The state protects copyright by ensuring a good investment environment such as preventing unfair competition; minimizing economic risk factors; contributes to forming the basis for the release of works and derivative works. For the users, it is sure that the original work is not repaired when delivered to the users (Thach & Duong, 2020).

OER

Open Educational Resources (OER) are teaching, learning or research materials that are in the public domain or released with intellectual property (IP) licenses that facilitate the free use, adaptation and distribution of resources (UNESCO, 2021). OER is a free learning resource available on the internet. OER brings many fundamental benefits to educational activities such as connecting faculty and students, helping to improve the quality of training and research, reducing the burden of additional funding, providing quality resources, and promoting transparency in academic activity. OER is publicly licensed or in the public domain and allows for free use or reuse (Nguyen, 2020). OER is simply an educational resource combined with a license, facilitating reuse and potential for adaptive customization, without the need for prior permission from the copyright holder (Le, 2019). OER can be books, training framework magazines, subject outlines, lectures, essays, tests, project results, videos, and animations. OER is like the type of printed or electronic document that each document is created has its own author, and it should also be copyright-respected when used by others. OER has an Open Access License/Creative Commons (CC) that will help the author protect his or her rights. Universities use this resource to serve the various training programs they are implementing, thereby supporting lecturers and students to easily access materials for teaching and learning activities (Do, 2019).

Open Access License/Creative Commons (CC)

Currently, many free/open license systems have been designed for free/open materials; however, two systems are typically mentioned: the GNU Free Document License (GFDL) and the Creative Commons (CC). GFDL license commonly used for materials that come with computer software programs. Meanwhile, CC licenses are widely used in all fields of science, technology, art and are the most used open access license system today (Le, 2016). More specifically, CC licenses are several copyright licenses issued on December 16, 2002 by Creative Commons, a U.S. non-profit company founded in 2001. The CC licensing system allows educational institutions, libraries to access, copy, reuse widely publicized works, which is not possible for protected works. CC license is a copyright license granted by the author or owner of a work for a work under the conditions set out in the license. In other words, CC licenses exist in parallel with copyright. The author and owner of the work still have the entire copyright of their own creation but through the use of the CC license, they claim to give up some of their monopolies and allow others to copy, clone or create derivative works (Dinh, 2019). CC licenses have important general features: helping creators - licensors - retain copyright, while allowing others to copy, distribute, and use the work - at least non-commercially. Each CC license also guarantees the licensee credit they deserve for their work. CC licenses have a global applicable scope and within the applicable copyright scope (as they are built on the basis of copyright). On the basis of these general features the licensee can choose to issue additional licenses when deciding how they want their work to be used (Cao, 2019). Basically, there are components used in CC. They are: Attribution (BY), Non-Commercial (NC), No Derivative (ND), and Share Alike (SA). From these four basic components, the CC license system consists of 6 types: (1) Attribution, (2) Attribution- Share Alike, (3) Attribution - No Derivative, (4) Attribution - Non-Commercial, (5) Attribution - Non-Commercial – Share Alike, and (6) Attribution – No Derivative - Non-Commercial. Each type of license

has its own functions, but what they have in common is that they require the user to credit the author. With each CC licensed document, the user simply needs to look at the symbols of the license and will understand how he or she will have to use the work. This allows the user to easily access the work and avoids the hassle of copyright issues. The user is responsible for complying with the rights that the license requires and a number of other requirements attached. Otherwise, this is considered a copyright infringement.

Literature review

The implementation of copyright in Vietnam still faces many difficulties and obstacles, especially copyright infringement (Vi Phong, 2019). The cause of copyright infringement in the academic environment is that students' perceptions of copyright infringement are not really clear. Sometimes they infringe copyright without knowing where they are infringing and the response of the library and information agencies in the University has not satisfied the needs of students (Nguyen, C. T., 2018). In addition, due to the lack of basic knowledge about copyright, students are quite confused when applying it into study and research; specifically, students do not know how to quote properly so as not to be considered to reenact other people's works or build references as appropriate (Nguyen. T. N. H., 2018). However, there are also some students who have knowledge of copyright law but do not yet know the specific approach to the terms in which the work is protected by copyright law for each different database. As a result, students often violate without knowing where they are violating during their use of information sources (Trinh, 2016). Currently, the regulations on violations of copyright still lack the system, not really complete and synchronous. There are still inappropriate regulations, especially with the development of the internet and the protection of copyright in the digital age (Nguyen, H. H., 2018). In addition, the reason for the student's copyright infringement as it is now also comes from the school. In the training program, the school does not have its own subject on IP or topics on IP in general and copyright in particular. The school has no specific sanctions on copyright violations and no popular propaganda activities on copyright (Nguyen, T. H. T., 2017).

In order to avoid copyright infringement, libraries need to promote dissemination of copyright knowledge to users, help them understand and comply with copyright laws (Bui & Bui, 2011). It is not enough to help students realize the importance of respecting copyright, universities need to develop standards of conduct to enforce respect for copyright through the exploitation and use of materials in teaching activities of lecturers, as well as student learning activities (Tran, 2016). In addition, the school should develop its own regulation on protection of copyright for its educational institutions, enhance the exchange of experiences in building regulations from other universities; it is necessary to develop technological measures so that subjects can effectively protect copyright; and specify the distribution of benefits between the author and the owner in the commercialization of works (Nguyen, T. N. T., 2019). In addition, school management should be paid attention to avoid violate the legitimate rights and interests of the author and owner of the works (Le et al., 2019). The implementation of copyright and the scope of legal protection for works at educational and training institutions will contribute to promoting innovative research activities, improving the quality of teaching and learning (Vu, 2020).

In addition, OER has seen as an effective solution to the current piracy problem because open access makes learning resources available online and allows students free access without paying. Due to the nature of the free access process, students will have easier access to new resources faster. This contributes to providing resources to help students learn and hone their skills better (Nguyen, D. M. T., 2017). In addition to having to leverage OER's strengths to create a free high-quality learning environment for all, lifelong learning through OER will bring many benefits to learners, help to improve professional knowledge and professional skills (Truong, 2017). Indeed, OER helps save costs but still ensures the quality of education. OER also has the ability to mobilize both lecturers and students into the creation and use of OER rather than just passive users (Nguyen, T. M. P., 2019). In the online learning environment, OER has become ideal for both students and the academics as they are both digital and can be embedded in the school's learning management systems. This also supports lecturers a lot in preparing lectures with training programs, remote training (Nguyen, 2020). Recognizing the potential of OER, many universities around the world have introduced students to use these resources. In particular, Brigham Young University students, USA exploited OER sources and appreciated the quality of materials on OER sources compared to traditional materials. This will help students save money to reinvest in their studies by purchasing materials for other courses. Meanwhile, students from Terbuka University, Indonesia rated OER sources as very useful, by watching videos where students can see examples of the topic they are studying in a real-life case. Besides, students find watching videos while studying by topic to be attractive, avoiding boredom rather than just reading printed material (Harsasi, 2015). In Bangladesh, faculties and students are motivated to use OER because it is found in the digital format, free availability, free of copyright and licensing restrictions (Mahmud et al., 2020).

Bond, Huddleston and Sapp (2021) found that the use of OER in classrooms has a similar or better effect on student learning outcomes as compared to traditional materials. It can also positively affect student retention, completion, and throughput rates, as well as student satisfaction. However, with diverse and rich resources, students will have difficulty choosing information, documents need to search according to the purpose of use. If they do not master a principle in exploiting, selecting, searching for information suitable for the purpose of use, they may be subject to information interference or not exploit all resources (Le, 2019). Therefore, to be able to exploit and use OER effectively, it is necessary to comply with the principles: search, select documents, check licenses and only download CC licensed resources and similar licenses (Mai & Nguyen, 2018). CC licenses are intended for the management of copyright in a digital environment, and often include copyright licenses, content generated by that license, and software tools to perform related work. CC licenses allow the creation of a community to create digital content, which is one of the effective ways to create OER (Cao, 2016). In addition to the need to adhere to the principles when exploiting OER users need to have core skills of finding, reusing, designing and disseminating them plays a very important role in the process of accessing and using OER (Nguyen, D. M. T., 2018).

Method

The study was carried out by quantitative method. The total number of librarianship students studying at Can Tho University is 266. As suggested by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the minimum sample size for this study is 159. The study uses random samples regardless of gender, class, or academic background. Each student has the opportunity to be invited to participate in a survey questionnaire. The number of samples from the junior (30%) and senior students (30%) are more than freshman (20%) and sophomore ones (20%). The study expects the junior and senior students to have more experiences and be able to provide richer data than the freshmen and sophomore ones.

Data collection methods

The study conducted surveys in class and online via Google form. To avoid duplication of information, the study requires students to respond only in one form of information collection. This means that if the student has responded to the printed form, they do not respond to the survey on Google Form.

Data Analysis Methods

The quantitative data collected will be systemized and analyzed using SPSS software. The SPSS functions such as frequency, percentage, and cross-comparison statistics were used to learn the students' knowledge and perceptions of OER protection. For open-question data, the study grouped thematic responses to facilitate analysis and solutions to raise awareness of librarianship students on OER copyright.

Findings

1. Librarianship students' understanding of copyright

Data of Table 2 shows that there is no difference between male and female students in their understanding of protected types of copyright, with more than 80% of students believing that literary, scientific and artistic works are protected works. The majority of students choose works of literature, science and art as the type protected copyright. Senior students (90.7%; n =39) get the highest proper understanding of the type of copyright protection and vice versa freshmen (67.6%; n = 23) has the lowest understanding rate of the type of protected type of copyright. In particular, the first year university students rank the highest rate (32.4%; n = 11) in believing that legal documents are the type of protected copyright. It is acceptable because they are new students in the university and do not have enough knowledge of copyright. Moreover, the group of students who studied Information Policy course had a 1.2 times higher rate of understanding the protected types of copyright than the group that had not studied. In addition, 24.2% (n =15) of students who choose the type of protection of copyright as legal documents are mainly students who have not studied Information Policy course. This finding shows that through the course, students have a more understanding and positive perception of copyright. Compared to students of An Giang University, 47.5% (n = 58) of them misunderstand the type of protection of copyright. They believed that news in newspapers and radio, legal documents, administrative documents are protected copyright works (Nguyen. T. N. H., 2018).

Table 2. The students' understanding of the types of protected copyright

Types of protected copyright		News		Literary, scientific and artistic works		Government documents	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
Gender	Male	1	2.9	29	82.9	5	14.3
	Female	0	0	106	84.8	19	15.2
	Senior	0	0	39	90.7	4	9.3

Students	Junior	0	0	42	87.5	6	12.5
	Sophomore	1	2.9	31	88.6	3	8.6
	Freshman	0	0	23	67.6	11	32.4
Information policy course	Learned	0	0	89	90.8	9	9.2
	Not yet	1	1.6	46	74.2	15	24.2

Research findings also show that the majority of librarianship students have a good awareness of the types of protection of copyright. However, there are still some students who are not well aware, especially the first year university students who have not studied Information Policy course. The majority of librarianship students understand the types of copyright protection correctly. It's a work of literature, science and art.

Intellectual property rights in general and copyright in particular are important in the educational environment. Below is the finding on the source of information to enrich students' knowledge about copyright (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Information sources of copyright

Data in Figure 1 shows differences in students' understanding according to the sources of information. The most prominent is the source of information from learning courses that help students know about copyright with more than 80% of senior, junior and freshmen. Compared to the students of the University of Transport Technology, only 21% ($n = 95$) students know copyright through the learning courses (Nguyen, T. H. T., 2017). It can be seen that librarianship teachers have done very well in integrating copyright issues into the subject, thereby students have better knowledge. In addition, media sources are the most selected source by senior students (79%), while junior and freshmen have an equal rate at 50%. Teachers are also the important sources providing copyright knowledge for the students with more than 60%. Meanwhile, friends are not considered as the good source of copyright because they score at the lowest rate, especially for freshmen (only 3%). Self-learning is not a good choice to gain knowledge of copyright just over 20%. Meanwhile, 46% ($n = 207$) students of the University of Transport Technology knew copyright freely (Nguyen, T. H. T., 2017). This proves that students of the University of Transport Technology are able to study on their own, find out copyright knowledge better than librarianship students at CTU do.

In general, learning courses are the good source of information that enriches librarianship students' knowledge about copyright. In addition, teachers and the media are sources with approximately the same selected proportions. Friends and self-study are the sources of information that do not dominate copyright for students. The majority of librarianship students know copyright through the teachers and courses. This shows that teachers play an important role in helping to improve students' understanding and awareness of copyright.

2. Librarianship students' understanding of OER

OER is increasingly affirming its value in supporting education training programs in the world, including Vietnam. Research findings about CTU librarianship students' understanding of OER are as follows.

Table 3. Librarianship students' understanding of OER

Recognition of OER	Number	%
No	119	74.7
Yes	19	11.9
Unsure	22	13.8
Concept of OER		
Understood correctly	18	11.2
Understood incorrectly	23	14.4

Data of Table 3 shows that the majority of librarianship students have not heard of OER (74.7%; n=119). Only a quarter of surveyed students (25.7%; n=41) have heard of this valuable source. About 13.8% (n=22) students have heard of OER but they do not know much about what OER is.

With one-third of students having heard of OER, only 10.6% (n=18) of them have a proper understanding of the concept of OER. They believe that OER are educational materials that are provided free of charge and legally on the internet for anyone to use, modify, share and redistribution. Fourth-year students (n=10) are the group of students who properly understand the concept of OER. In contrast, 13.8% (n=22) of students said OER is a free learning resource available on the internet, without copyright, and that anyone can use it. Compared to students of Hanoi National University (VNU), 34% (n = 65) of VNU students were aware of the existence of OER. Nearly 50% (n = 95) of students had exploited OER sources for academic purposes. In particular, this group of students regularly exploits OER sources from Vietnamese projects (20%). In addition, 25% of students understood the concept of OER. Nearly 45% (n=80) of students agree and strongly agree with the idea that all free and open access materials are considered OER (Do, 2019). Meanwhile, students of Da Nang Vocational College very often use OER or participate in projects related to OER (45.6%; n =31), and 33.8% (n =23) of students frequently use OER. More than 40% of students use OER sources for learning activities and expanding new knowledge updates while only 25% of students use OER sources for scientific research and participation in online learning forums (Le, 2019).

Thus, compared to students of these two universities, the majority of librarianship students have not heard of OER, the percentage of students who do not know about CC is 3 times higher than the percentage of students who have known OER. More particularly, for students who already know OER, very few students understand the concept of OER correctly. The ratio between misunderstanding right and misunderstanding about OER is not very high. The majority of librarianship students don't understand the concept of OER correctly. These students claim that OER is a free learning resource available on the internet, without copyright and anyone can use it. In fact, OER sources must be properly understood as educational materials provided free of charge and legally on the Internet for anyone to be able to reuse, modify, share and redistribution provided that the author's credit is at least required.

One of the key factors for OER to share and use widely and conveniently is the license system that comes with this resource. An open license is a type of license that states that the user of the work is allowed to use, modify and share under the defined terms and conditions. This license is attached to original works or derivative works. This allows the user to actively access the works and use it proactively based on a license without having to contact the author.

Table 4. Students' understanding of OER

Knowing OER	Number	%
No	146	91.2
Yes	6	3.8
Unsure	8	5.0

Data of Table 4 shows that the majority of librarianship students do not know open access licenses (91.2%; n = 146). Meanwhile, only 8.8% (n = 14) of students who know about open access licenses. In particular, 5% (n=8) of students, despite knowing an open access license, still do not really understand what an open access license means. On the other hand, in being compared to the data of VNU students, 18.1% (n = 34) of them, twice as high as the group of librarianship students at VNU understood the concept of open use licenses. This finding helps to state that the H0 hypothesis is correct. More than 90% of librarianship students are unaware of the types of licenses for OER sources.

Figure 2. Students' understanding of CC

Data in Figure 2 shows that the percentage of students who have encountered some symbol of an open access license during internet searches is 3.1% (n=5). In addition, the number of students who already know about open access symbols, as well as know the meaning of these symbols has an equal rate of 0.6% (n=1). In other words, only 1 student out of 160 students knows and fully understands the meaning of the 6 symbols of open access license. This finding shows that the percentage of students who are aware of open access licenses is extremely low: only one student knows about open access permits. The lack of knowledge about open access permits is also one of the reasons students infringe on OER copyright. During internet searches it is possible that the student has encountered symbols of open access licenses but due to lack of knowledge about these types of licenses and not understanding the meaning of symbols should lead to OER copyright infringement without students' knowledge.

3. Copyright violations against OER

Infringing on copyright is the act of appropriating, copying, impersonating the author, publishing, distributing the work, repairing, mutilating or misrepresenting the work, harming the honor and reputation of the author without the author's consent.

Table 5. Students' copyright violations against OER

Copyright violations	Number	%
1. Using full text without citation	31	6.2
2. Using information on Internet without citation	60	12
3. Downloading & sharing other people's information without citation	80	16
4. Attributing & derivating for commercial purposes	15	3
5. Citing without citation	65	13
6. Copying & shortening other people's research without citation	37	7.4
7. Copying, editing, blending & sharing original work without commercial and citation	54	10.8
8. Remixing, revising & building the original works to create derivative works that are not for commercial purposes but do not reuse licenses like the licenses granted to the original works	28	5.6
9. Repairing original works for commercial purposes and citation	19	3.8
10. Repairing & remixing original works without commercial purposes & citation	27	5.4
11. Repairing & reconstructing of original works not used for commercial purposes & without reusing licenses like the licenses granted for the original work	22	4.4
12. Downloading or sharing the original works without commercial purposes & citation	62	12.4

Data of Table 5 shows that students commit the highest violations against OER in downloading documents and sharing them without citation (16%; n = 80). In the meanwhile, extracting paragraph without citation ranks at 13% (n = 65). In addition, using information on the Internet and downloading or sharing the original work without citation and not using it for commercial purposes have approximately the same rate (over 10%). Students also copy, edit, mix and share the content of original works without charge and without attributing sources (10.8%; n = 54). Librarianship students' copyright violation have similarities with students of VNU. Specifically, up to 55.3% (n = 105) VNU students agreed that they do not pay much attention to copyright and licenses when using materials online. In addition, this group of students said that they did not pay much attention to plagiarism issues and citations during their studies (45.7%; n = 87) and more than 30% (n = 42) students supported the idea that there was no need to quote when using free material (Do, 2019).

In contrast to the above behaviors, other behaviors have a low rate of student violations. In particular, repairing the original works for business purposes and with citation get the low violation rate (3.8%; n = 19). Also, repairing and rebuilding the original works without commercial purposes and reusing the same license as the license granted to the original works score at a low rate (4.4%; n = 22). Similarly, repairing and remixing the original works for commercial purposes is the act with the lowest rate of student violations (3%; n = 15).

These findings show that some students still infringe copyright. The most common violation is using OER without citation. This is an alarming situation for the Department of Library and Information Management. The majority of librarianship students still have the most common piracy violations of not being credited when quoting information from OER.

Figure 3. Copyright violations against OER

Data of Figure 3 shows that downloading documents and sharing them without citation have approximately the same rate of over 20%. In particular, the senior student violation rate is also the percentage of sophomore students violating (26.2%; n = 21), and the percentage of junior students violating is equal to the rate of violations of the first-year university students (23.8%; n = 19). Meanwhile, using information on the internet without citation has a marked difference. Senior students had the highest rate of violations at 31.7% (n=19), twice as high as sophomore students (25%), and junior students had nearly the same percentage of offending freshmen. In addition, students also commit copyright violations against OER that are coding paragraph without citing. Senior students are also the ones with the highest percentage of violators (32.3%; n = 21), 1.7 times higher than junior (18.5%). Meanwhile, sophomore student violation rate of 29.2% (n=19) was 1.5 times higher than freshmen (20%). In addition, downloading or sharing the original works without attribution and not being used for commercial purposes reaches a high rate of over 20%. In the meanwhile, junior students are the highest percentage of violators at 29% (n = 18), and freshmen are the lowest percentage of violators (21%; n = 13), approximately with the number of junior students violating (22.6%; n = 14). Overall, the percentage of students violating copyright reached over 20%. Fourth-year students are the highest group of students in violation, followed by the second-year students. Meanwhile, third-year students and first-year students had lower rates of violations than the others. Most notably, third-year students were the lowest group of students in violation.

Table 6. Solutions to help raise awareness for students about copyright for OER

Solution	n/160	%
1. Propagating to users of copyright	154	96.3
2. Instructing students how to use OER	154	96.3
3. Lecturers include copyright in the course	150	93.8
4. Improving students' knowledge about copyright through social network	146	91.3
5. Using anti-plagiarism software	140	87.5
6. Organizing seminars on copyright	134	83.8
7. Conducting course of copyright	128	80
8. Applying sanctions	113	70.6

Data in Table 6 shows that the library needs to propagate copyright and instructs the users how to use OER. These are the most voted solution (96.3%; n = 154). This finding confirms the very important role of libraries in increasing users' awareness of OER. In addition, the solution that teachers should integrate copyright into the course gets the high vote with 93.8% (n = 150). Another solution is social networking to disseminate knowledge to students about copyright (91.3%; n = 146). It can be seen that with the development of technology, social networking is considered an effective channel to propagate copyright to students. In addition, some other

solutions are to conduct the course of copyright (80%; n = 128) and applying sanctions (70.6%; n = 113). In general, the majority of students agree with the proposed solutions. This shows that the students are also aware of the importance of respecting copyright for OER. The proposed solutions will partly reduce the level of piracy among students as it is today.

Moreover, the study also obtained 36 proposals for solutions to raise awareness for librarianship students about copyright from open questions. Specifically, on the school's side, students have proposed to open short-term classes to teach about copyright to students from the beginning of their admission, need to have their own subjects on copyright and severely punish for copyright violations, and propose to integrate the contents of copyright into seminar activities. Regarding the role of teachers, teachers need to learn about copyright to propagate to students and can mention copyright during teaching. In addition, teachers need to update and supplement their knowledge about copyright and then disseminate it to students. In particular, teachers should give a score of 0 with non-sourced articles. To the students, they themselves need to actively implement the copyright protection policy, limit plagiarism by not arbitrarily plagiarism, copy when using other people's works and have to ask permission, as well as specify the source.

Conclusions and Suggestions

OER is being considered as an effective source of scientific information to support training programs. Research findings show that librarianship students' understanding of OER is very limited. The majority of students have never heard of OER while a small number of students know the OER concept correctly. In addition, less than ten percent of research participating students know the open access permits. Besides, a large number of students do not know the symbols of open access licenses as well as the meaning of these symbols. It may be caused by the students' lack of knowledge about OER and the understanding of open access licenses, which leads them to infringe copyright unintentionally.

The school therefore needs to have its own teaching course on copyright. In addition, the university needs to organize training for lecturers on intellectual property to have general knowledge about intellectual property and disseminate it to students. The university may post information related to OER copyright on the university's website or use social networking sites to disseminate information to students. In addition, the university should have regulations on plagiarism and have specific sanctions for OER copyright infringement. The university may establish a department to address OER piracy issues within the school. More specifically, the school library needs to propagate to users the knowledge of copyright and OER.

Moreover, lecturers should master copyright and OER to disseminate it to students. Lecturers usually contact with students and have certain impact on them. It is very effective for lecturers to re-propagate their insights on these issues to students. In addition, lecturers can integrate copyright and OER content into their subjects. They should introduce students to OER resources, how to harness this rich resource as well as understand the meaning of open access licenses. Through the academic club, lecturers need to create useful playgrounds of copyright for students, responding to the annual World Book or the International Day of the book and Copyright Day (23/4) to organize competitions to learn about copyright and OER or to make video clips related to IP Law. Moreover, lecturers in the Information Policy course should organize seminars on copyright and OER to help students more aware of this valuable source in their study and research.

Especially, students themselves should learn and improve their knowledge about copyright and OER. It is important for students to quote the source when referencing the others' works. Moreover, students need to actively implement the policy of protecting copyright, propagating to friends and relatives about respecting copyright.

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